

The Effect of Temperature Change on Agricultural Productivity and Efficiency in West Vidarbha – A Geographical Analysis

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Abstract

The increase in temperature is found to be more or less the same in all the regions and the effects of this increase in temperature are seen in different areas. Various factors are responsible for the rise in temperature. Rising temperatures, illegal deforestation, overpopulation, industrialization, increased use of electronics, etc., have contributed to the rise in temperature. Temperature rise has a direct effect on rainfall distribution and has a direct effect on agricultural productivity and efficiency. Rising temperatures have eroded most of the agricultural land, while high temperatures have burned crops. The last few decades have seen an increase in global warming and its impact on agriculture. Although the agricultural yield has increased in some areas, the agricultural yield per hectare i.e. agricultural productivity has decreased. Present paper has discussed the impact of temperature change in agricultural productivity and efficiency in the West Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state.

Key Words: Temperature, Change, Climate, Agriculture, Productivity, Efficiency, Effect

Introduction

West Vidarbha includes the Amravati division of the state of Maharashtra. The region consists of five districts namely Amravati, Akola, Washim, Buldhana and Yavatmal. West Vidarbha is known as the tropical region of Maharashtra. Summer temperatures in the region are found to be above average. In the present paper, the district wise study of changes in the average temperature in West Vidarbha for the years 1991 and 2021 and the agricultural productivity index and efficiency index during this period has been studied. West Vidarbha has seen a rise in temperature but a slight decline in agricultural productivity and efficiency. This means that the temperature rise has adversely affected the agricultural sector in the study area.

Objectives

The particular objectives of the present research paper as follows,

- 1) To discuss the change in temperature, agricultural productivity, and efficiency in the study region
- 2) To analysis the effect of temperature change on agricultural productivity and efficiency in the study region

Data Source and Methodology

The analysis of the present research work is mainly based on the secondary source. The related information and data is collected from Divisional Agricultural office, Amravati, Crop Report, and Regional metrological Department, Nagpur. Agricultural productivity is calculated by Mohammad Shafi's method with the use of following formula,

$$\text{Agricultural Productivity} = (Y \div Y_n) \div (T \div T_n)$$

Y = Production in unit area, Y_n = Production in total area, T = Crop area in unit area, T_n = crop area in total region

The agricultural efficiency index is calculated by Ganguli's method with the help of following formula,

$$E_n = (I_{yn} \times C_n) \div 100$$

E_n – Agricultur Efficiency Index, I_{yn} – Yeild of Crop, C_n – Crop Land Share in Percentage

Change in temperature, productivity and efficiency is calculated by using following formula,

$$\text{Change} = \text{Current Year Value} - \text{Last Known Year Value}$$

The present discussion is based on the year 1991 and 2021. All collected and calculated values presented on the table and results presented in the maps and graphs.

Study Region

Study region i.e. West Vidarbha region is also known as Amravati division. There are total fives districts are included in this region. Amravati, Yavatmal, Akola, Washim and Buldhana. The region is situated in between 19° 23' N to 21° 43' N latitude and 75° 57' E to 79° 09' E longitudes.

Total geographical area of the study region is 46547 Sq.Km. and its share is 14.75% to the total geographical area of Maharashtra state. Total population of the region is 11258117 according to the year 2011 census,

Average Temperature in West Vidarbha

The average annual temperature in the West Vidarbha region is occurred in between 26° to 28° Celsius. West Vidarbha region falls in tropics, the temperature in this region is hot. West Vidarbha has the highest temperature in all the districts in the month of April end and complete

May. In West Vidarbha, the rainy season is cloudy while the dry season is mostly clear. In Vidarbha, the minimum temperature in winter is 12⁰ Celsius and the maximum temperature in summer rises up to 45⁰ Celsius. But in the year

2021 and 2022 the maximum temperature in summer rises up to 48⁰ Celsius in some districts.

District wise Average Temperature in West Vidarbha

District wise average annual temperature in the year 1991 and 2021 is shown in the table no 1.

Table No 1, District wise Average Temperature in West Vidarbha Region in the Year 1991 & 2021

Districts	Average Annual Temperature in Degree Celsius (1991)	Average Annual Temperature in Degree Celsius (2021)
Buldhana	23.7	25.3
Akola	25.6	27.4
Washim	27.1	27.9
Amravati	26.4	27.2
Yavatmal	26.01	27.6
Total Region	26.11	27.13

Source – Regional Metrological Department, Nagpur

There are several changes occurred in the average temperature of the study region during the period 1991 to 2011. In the year 1991 total temperature of the study region found 26.11⁰ C and in 2021 it found 27.13⁰ C. In the year 1991 the average temperature is found more than 20⁰ C in all districts. The maximum average

temperature is recorded in Washim district 27.1⁰ C and lower temperature is recorded in Washim district 23.7⁰ C. In Amravati (26.4⁰ C) and Yavatmal (26.01⁰ C) found the temperature in between 26 to 27⁰ C, while Akola (25.6⁰ C) district found in between 25 to 26⁰ C.

The Average temperature of West Vidarbha region is 27.11⁰ C in the year 2011 and it rises compare to the year 1991. This year also the highest temperature is occurred in Washim district 27.9⁰ C. The average temperature is found more than 25⁰ C in all districts in the year 2021. Buldhana district again recorded the low average temperature 25.3⁰ C in 2021 compare to other districts of the study region. In remaining districts the average temperature is recorded more than 27⁰ C. Although the district-wise distribution is uneven, the average temperature

in 2021 has increased in every district compared to 1991. Most of the Buldhana district is hilly so the temperature is a little lower there. Also, Amravati has the highest amount of natural vegetation in West Vidarbha. But the average temperature has increased due to continuous illegal deforestation.

Agricultural Productivity in West Vidarbha

District wise agricultural productivity index in the year 1991 and 2011 is shown in table no 2.

Table No 2
District wise Agricultural Productivity in West Vidarbha (1991 & 2021)

Districts	Agricultural Productivity Index (1991)	Agricultural Productivity Index (2021)
Buldhana	1.12	0.87
Akola	1.14	1.02
Washim	0.99	0.92
Amravati	1.03	0.91
Yavatmal	1.26	1.06
Total Region	1.09	0.95

Source – Productivity index is calculated by author

The productivity index of the total region is found 1.09 in the year 1991 and in 2021 it found 0.95. The production is increased but the ratio of production in per yield is decreased during last two decades. The variations are found in district wise productivity index in both years 1991 and 2011 due to the uneven cultivated area and sources of irrigation. In the year 1991 highest productivity index is found in Yavatmal district 1.26 and low productivity is found in Washim district 0.99. In other all district this productivity index is found more than 1. In the year Yavatmal district again found the maximum index of

productivity 1.06, compare to the other districts of the region. But per yield production is slightly decreased in 2021 than 1991. In the year 2021 Buldhana (0.87) found the lowest index of productivity in the entire region. Amravati (0.91) and Washim (0.92) also found this index less than 1. The index is found more than 1 only in Yavatmal (1.06) and Akola (1.02) districts. In Yavatmal district there are more irrigation projects and as a lot of the land is flat, the agricultural productivity is higher than in other districts.

Agricultural Efficiency in West Vidarbha

The district wise agricultural efficiency index is presented in table no 3 of the year 1991 and 2011.

Table No 3
District wise Agricultural Efficiency in West Vidarbha (1991 & 2021)

Districts	Agricultural Efficiency Index (1991)	Agricultural Efficiency Index (2021)
Buldhana	23.52	23.41
Akola	15.81	15.45
Washim	13.63	13.12
Amravati	19.32	18.22
Yavatmal	24.68	23.95
Total Region	19.36	18.74

Source – Efficiency index is calculated by author

The agricultural efficiency index in the study region also shows a decline similar to the productivity index. In the year 1991, the agricultural efficiency index of Sampur region was 19.36 and in 2021 it was found to be 18.74. In the year 1991 Yavatmal district is recorded maximum efficiency index 24.68 and then it found in Buldhana 23.52. The index in these districts is more than 20. Washim district found lowest efficiency index 13.63 and in other district the efficiency index is recorded in between 15 to 20. In then year 2021 the efficiency index is decreased in all districts of

the region. This year also Yavatmal (23.95) and Buldhana (23.41) districts found higher value of efficiency index, more than 20. Washim district again recorded lower value of this index 13.12. Other districts in the region found this index in between 15 to 20 and it is almost same as 1991. But the efficiency is quite decreased in all over the region.

Change in Average Temperature, Agricultural Productivity and Efficiency

District wise changes in these factors are shown in table no 4.

Table No 4
Change in Average Temperature, Agricultural Productivity and Efficiency
in West Vidarbha (1991 to 2021)

Districts	Change in Average Temperature (Degree Celsius)	Change in Agricultural Productivity Index (1991)	Change in Agricultural Efficiency Index
Buldhana	+1.60	-0.25	-0.11
Akola	+1.80	-0.12	-0.36
Washim	+0.80	-0.07	-0.51
Amravati	+0.80	-0.12	-1.1
Yavatmal	+1.59	-0.20	-0.73
Total Region	+1.02	-0.14	-0.62

Source – Change is calculated by author

Change in Average Temperature

During the period 1991 to 2021 total 1.02⁰ C, but its ratio is not uniform in all districts. Maximum growth of temperature in Akola district 1.8⁰ C and then Buldhana 1.6⁰ C and Yavatmal district

1.59⁰ C. In Washim and Amravati district average temperature rises up to 0.8⁰ C during the period 1991 to 2021. The growth in average temperature shows the increasing amount of pollution in the entire region.

Change in Agricultural Productivity

There are negative changes occurred in agricultural productivity in the whole region. The productivity index is decreased in all districts of the region. Actually the agriculture production is increases but per yield production is not increased compare to the growth of cultivated land in the region. Therefore this index is found less than 1991in 2021. In the entire region the index is decreased by 0.14

during 1991 to 2021. Maximum negative change is occurred in Buldhana (-0.25) and then in Yavatmal (-0.20) district. The lowest negative change is occurred in Washim district -0.07. In Washim district, the amount of temperature increase is less compared to other districts, so the agricultural productivity is slightly reduced.

Change in Agricultural Efficiency

The efficiency index value is decreased by 0.62 during the period 1991 to 2021. The efficiency

index is decreased in all districts of the region. The efficiency and productivity is like the two sides of one coin. The highest efficiency is decreased in Amravati district and it shows that the agricultural productivity of Amravati district has decreased due to the decrease in agricultural efficiency in this district. Also, the agricultural production is not compared to the agricultural efficiency of this district. Buldhana district has the lowest rate of efficiency loss and in all districts except Amravati, this index is less than

Effect of Temperature Change on Agricultural Productivity and Efficiency

The effect of change in temperature on the agricultural productivity and efficiency is presented with correlation between them. The relation between change in temperature and change in agricultural productivity is negative ($r = -0.60$). It means the change in temperature is not so much impact on the agricultural productivity. But the relation between change in temperature and change in agricultural efficiency is positive ($r = +0.23$) and it low degree positive.

It means the rising temperature is directly impact on the efficiency of agriculture in the study region. The increasing temperature decreases the efficiency of agriculture. The reducing agricultural efficiency effects on the agricultural productivity in the region. That is, although rising temperatures do not have a direct impact on agricultural productivity, they do have an indirect impact, because rising temperatures have reduced agricultural efficiency, and reduced agricultural efficiency has reduced agricultural productivity. The relationship between these two factors is shown with the help of regression line.

Conclusions and Suggestions

In West Vidarbha, the average temperature has increased in every district during the period 1991 to 2021. Also, due to continuous illegal deforestation in forest areas like Melghat in Amravati district, the temperature of the district has increased and it has directly affected agriculture. The forest region of western Vidarbha is rich in natural resources, but the climate of the region has been affected the most due to deforestation in the region. West Vidarbha has increased by more than 10°C from 1991 to 2021. Yavatmal district has the highest number of irrigation projects, yet the rate of decline in

agricultural productivity and efficiency is high. The main reason for this is the rise in temperature in the district. Buldhana district as well as northern part of Yavatmal district is a water scarce region. Akola and Washim also face water drought in summer. If the rise in temperature is not stopped in time, this crisis will worsen in the future. It is necessary to stop illegal deforestation and increase natural vegetation cover. Today considering the seriousness of global temperature rise it is necessary to reduce pollution and also to increase the amount of forests in every area as it will balance the climate and thus increase agricultural efficiency and increase agricultural production.

References

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